

EFFICIENT HETEROGENEOUS THREE-DIMENSIONAL PACKAGING AT A SYSTEM LEVEL

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ABSTRACT

While a proliferation of approaches have been proposed for three-dimensional packaging, a basic dichotimization between short stacks of regular (low-complexity) iterated assemblies and heterogeneous approaches exist. For the latter, no clear order exists, which has stifled the true acceptance of three-dimensional packaging. Barriers to advancement of heterogeneous are discussed. Two basic approaches are examined.

INTRODUCTION

Efficiencies in packaging are central in the cases where miniaturization are important, and typical application regimes include small spacecraft, missiles, and sub-munitions. Any comprehensive attack on the problem of miniaturization in electronics systems cannot fail to consider the technologies of advanced packaging. While most often, multi-chip module (MCM) approaches are considered, they are not a complete answer in most cases, especially for systems that cannot be housed onto a single MCM. In that case, choices are limited to: (1) increasing the size of the MCM to incorporate all electronics in a design; (2) arranging multiple packages onto printed wiring boards (PWBs), or (3) implement a three-dimensional (3-D) MCM packaging approach. While this assessment is simplistic, since sometimes the distinction between PWBs and MCMs can be blurred, it serves as a basis for further consideration of the packaging problem that is faced in the challenge of complex electronics systems miniaturization.

Of the three options, the 3-D MCM approach could be the best answer if certain issues in implementation were addressed. This paper

examines how approaches might be made in 3-D packaging in which the following issues are addressed:

- maximum volumetric component density
- mixed "domains" within an assembly (e.g., analog, digital, microwave, power)
- thermal management
- structural / environmental
- integration with anything else (e.g., sensors, actuators, platform facilities for power, communication)
- ease of access of sub-components within the 3-D assembly

To do this, a brief examination of other non-3D MCM complex integration approaches will be discussed, as this is the current practice for the most part. Next, a quick review of current 3-D MCM approaches will be performed. A dichotomy is observed between stacked memory and "almost anything else". The primary emphasis of the present paper will be on a potential solution space for high-efficiency microsystem 3-D packaging approaches. This framework takes advantage of the best MCM technologies, but is not restricted to them. The framework permits access to sub-components with minimal concessions to density. Furthermore, this 3-D framework permits the mixture of functional "domains". In this manner, these approaches could achieve a commoditization effect, allowing a wide class of high density packaging approaches to be co-integrated. For these reasons, the frameworks can be referred to as *3-D heterogeneous packaging approaches*.

CURRENT PRACTICES

This section examines the options for complex integration that are not strictly regarded as 3-D MCM approaches. Here,

complex integration problems are those that have more electronics than can be accommodated in a small planar MCM and / or require the co-integration of components not traditionally found in those MCMs. It is not simple to establish strict quantitative definitions of "3-D MCMs" and "small", due to the changing nature of the packaging field. For the purposes of the present discussion, it should suffice to indicate that 3-D MCMs are technologies where planar MCMs are arranged in stacks with a vertical pitch between layers much smaller than traditional board assemblies, say < 5mm. Similarly, "small" MCMs could be defined as < 40mm, crossing into a region referred to as "few chip MCMs".

The basic approaches for non 3-D MCM approaches to achieve complex integration include larger MCMs and configurations involving multiple MCMs.

Larger MCMs

The use of large MCMs seems to be a "more is better" approach to miniaturization. The advantages of large MCMs are similar to the advantages of large integrated circuits (ICs) in monolithic systems development. Breaking the boundary to the next level of packaging, whether it is from an IC die or an MCM assembly, involves engaging a number of interconnection structures which are by definition less efficient, which affects size, weight, power consumption, and performance adversely. The most obvious disadvantage of large MCMs is in a much exacerbated component yield problem. A simplified analysis reveals a relationship between module yield and substrate size:

$$Y = y^{(l/a)^2 \eta}$$

where Y is module yield, y is component yield, l is substrate size, a is IC die size, and η is substrate efficiency. Yield plots as a function of substrate length for different MCM types is presented Figure 1, illustrating the difficulty in obtaining adequate yield in large MCMs (example

Figure 1. Impact of substrate size on component yield.

assumes 99% component yield and 0.5 cm die size and mid-range substrate efficiencies¹ of representative MCM classes).

But large MCMs create other impositions in conventional packaging strategies, which involve placing MCMs onto printed wiring boards (PWBs), which are placed into a chassis. Large MCMs usually require reinforcement of the board and mounting structure, expand more under thermal stress, and "steal" more space for placement of other complex components, resulting in a loss of efficiency at the next packaging level that mitigates the gains afforded by the MCM itself. Large MCMs do not promote efficient system packaging strategies in general, unless most of the system is actually contained within the MCM.

Multiple MCMs

Complex systems that cannot be accommodated within a single MCM can be partitioned into multiple MCMs. In common practice, when this partition is done, the MCMs are co-integrated onto PWBs or separate PWBs within a chassis. The packaging structures between separate MCMs on a PWB and between ICs within an MCM are depicted in Figure 2. The increase in the size and number of the conductor structures in the PWB interface necessarily reduce the intimate interconnection capability possible within a single MCM boundary. Between separate PWBs, the situation is much worse, as other interconnection structures are introduced, and average path lengths between circuit terminals are much

longer. The penalty exacted by these arrangements on volumetric efficiencies are severe, due to spacing requirements between packages laterally arranged onto a PWB and the distance between individual PWBs within a system chassis. Newer classes of high-performance electronics assemblies such as PCI mezzanine busses and PCMCIA cards have considerably improved density, but must set headroom spacing to target many different types of component packages, and these standards are predominately limited in the number of conductors and the types of signals that can be impressed upon them without compromising waveform integrity.

Figure 2. Comparison of MCM-to-MCM and IC-to-IC (within an MCM) interconnection structures.

3-D MCM APPROACHES

Almost without exception, 3-D MCMs are formed through stacks of planar ICs or MCMs. The stacking of individual ICs exploits simple, regular architectures, such as memories, which require a limited number

Figure 3. Irvine Sensors Corporation "short-stack" technology.

of conductors be routed between layers. A celebrated form of 3-D IC stacking is shown

in Figure 3, in which an overlay structure is formed onto ICs to redistributed conductors to one edge. Groups of individual chips are united by stacking, bringing all connections to one edge surface, which is interconnected to form a compact 3-D structure, no larger and not much thicker than a bare IC die.

Many other 3-D approaches follow a *short format* stacking approach with individual die, i.e., a stacking approach consisting of four or fewer layers. This arrangement is convenient, since it represents a next-generation in memory density and short format stacks integrate well into some existing single chip memory package formats.

Stacks of identical chips with many layers are less common, but are sometimes found in aerospace applications for memory and exotic sensor applications. The popularity of short format IC stacking, memories in particular, constitutes a polarization of sorts in 3-D packaging. Whether or not a "critical mass" is being approached in short format memory stacks, nothing else in 3-D packaging technologies comes close to a trend. The remainder of this section considers the variants of 3-D packaging which have been manifested in research.

3-D MCMs, as a diverse class of 3-D packaging technology, is descriptive of substrate stacking approaches, ranging from the degenerate case (single chip) to the very complex (stacks of complex MCMs or specialized 3D arrangements of 3D MCM segments). While chip stacking requires die of homogeneous size and input / output (I/O) conductor terminals, 3-D MCMs impose these requirements on the substrate rather than individual components. As such, a much greater variety of components and functions are easily accommodated. One of the first complex heterogeneous 3-D MCM processes demonstrated was based on a 3-D extension of the HDI patterned overlay process, shown in Figure 5. Here, a collection of identically sized HDI modules

are assembled as a dense 3-D block, which can be placed within an enclosure or further enhanced by the addition of components and interfaces to the top and edge faces. An

Figure 5. 3-D HDI as an example of a heterogeneous 3-D MCM process. (a) Arrangement of pre-fabricated 2-D HDI MCMs. (b) Layer attach and addition of edge overlays. (c) Edge interconnection system formed [1].

alternate 3-D MCM approach involves the stacking of substrates with electrical feedthroughs via an interposing mechanism which provides compliance, as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Longitudinal cross-section of 3-D MCM approach involving mechanically-compliant interposer-spacers.

Attributes of 3-D Packaging Approaches

Layer-to-Layer Connection. An important characteristic of 3-D packaging approaches is the manner by which signals are distributed between layers. The primary mechanisms, shown in Figure 4, are plane-plane and edge-plane approaches. In 3-D systems, both approaches are used. The example shown in Figure 5 employs the plane-edge interconnection system, while Figure 6 depicts a system that employs a

plane-plane connection system. Further examination on the connection arrangements reveals that while edge-plane approaches limit the number of substrate-to-substrate connections to order l/p , where l is substrate dimension and p is pitch between conductors, in theory a plane-plane approach achieves order $(l/p)^2$ connections, due to

Figure 4. 3-D connections. (a) Plane-plane. (b) Edge-plane.

more available area for placement of interconnections. Potential drawbacks in plane-plane systems include: (1) the competition between interconnection and component for surface area, and (2) the problem of blocked conductors in multi-layer routing of point-to-point connections. The latter problem is manifested in stacks that contain many layers where point-to-point connections are needed randomly amongst layers. To route a connection, for example, from the fifth layer to the tenth layer of a stack requires that layers six through nine also pass the same connection. Intuitively, it is obvious that a complex assembly can quickly consume most available conductor channels through intermediate layers. Edge-plane systems, on the other hand, do not have this problem, but have a restriction on the total number of channels.

Iterational Arrangement. The manner in which layers are stacked or, in essence, what makes a particular approach “3-D”, is an attribute referred to as “iterational arrangement”. The iterational arrangement at the simplest extreme can be a double-sided substrate or, at the most complicated extreme, a compound, repeating assembly ---

literally a stack of MCMs within other MCMs. A summary of iterational arrangements follows:

- **Double-sided** - using both sides of a planar mounting surface.
- **Repeatable** - configurations that are theoretically extensible to an arbitrary limit.
- **Telescoping** - stair-step stacking technique. A "Towers of Hanoi" assembly is shown in Figure 7a. Repeatable telescoping structures have also been demonstrated.

Figure 7. Odd iterational arrangements. (a) Towers of Hanoi. (b) Folded MCM.

- **Folding** - non-planar assembly of planar-fabricated layers, which are folded on portions of interconnecting system that do not contain components (Figure 7b).
- **Compound** - MCMs within MCMs.

Separable Layers. The ability to service all but the most trivial 3-D assemblies appears to be a requirement in many cases. Non-separable 3-D approaches either: (1) cannot be separated without destroying layers or components, or (2) could be separated only by destroying the interconnection system between layers. The need of separability is met with interposers. *Interposers* are a generic term for compliant contact multi-conductor systems that interface between conductors on two surfaces. Such compliance is necessary to permit non-planarity and differential expansion of surfaces to be accommodated. Separable and non-separable system examples are represented in Figure 4 and Figure 5, respectively.

EFFICIENT SYSTEM PACKAGING CHALLENGES

If a requirement exists for system-level miniaturization, then obviously all functions within a contemporary electronics system must be targeted as elements of the

packaging approach. Here, the low-profile die stacking technologies fail as a general strategy, and in fact most MCM / 3-D packaging research efforts address a relatively simple application domain: sub-200 MHz saturating digital logic. The challenges of creating a workstation chipset core or dense memory differ substantially from the challenge of handling a system where low-level analog, rf / microwave, and power functions of varying levels of thermal dissipation are required. In space applications, there are furthermore issues of outgassing, radiation environments, and limited thermal management options. This section examines a number of the challenges in the miniaturization of highly complex systems of general or heterogeneous function. The basis of much of this work stems from previous Phillips Laboratory (PL) work in 3-D HDI and other packaging approaches, short-form stacking, and the Monolithic Interceptor Processor (MiP) feasibility study in which the aggressive miniaturization of a next-generation interceptor was examined.

Density / Extensibility. It has been remarked that an average electronics system is less than 1% efficient by volume². Even the introduction of MCMs alone does not remarkably improve density. The introduction of 3-D packaging is a deliberate attempt to improve efficiency over printed wiring board (PWB) approaches, such as VME and SEM-E³ form factors. These approaches use liberal board-to-board pitch spacing to accommodate large packages and bulky components that are typically mounted to PWBs. Any 3-D systems approach must similarly deal with these issues. MCMs allow a convenient means to eliminate bulky IC packages, but may not solve the problem associated with large capacitors, transformers, etc.

Electrical performance. It is difficult to conceive of a single interconnection system that can deal with divergent electrical requirements within a complex system. The

discipline of signal integrity engineering has emerged in high-performance digital systems designs, but low-level analog, microwave, and power have special requirements as summarized in Table 1. Beyond this the need for impedance control exists in microwave assemblies, and for digital the move to dense 3-D packaging can reduce the critical dimensions for which impedance control is necessary.

Table 1. Signal integrity requirements for different regions of performance.

Region	Density	Isolation	Series loss
Analog	Medium	<1/2LSB	Low
Digital	High	< 20db	non-crit
Microwave	Low	High	Low
Power	Low	High	Low!

Electrical Interface. The number of I/O is problematic at various levels of design, whether monolithic, MCM, or in 3-D packaging. "Pad-limiting", as commonly encountered, forces the size of assembly to be larger than necessary due to the need to accommodate large numbers of I/O.

Thermal management / Power Reduction. Without re-engineering ICs, reductions in size and weight quickly outpace power reductions, leading to net increase in power density. There are two splits in heat removal for a 3-D system correlated with short-form and "many layer" 3-D systems. As illustrated in Figure 8, the addition of layers increases the thermal path of each successive layer, making necessary the consideration of lateral heat removal.

Figure 8. Effect of layer count on thermal management.

Testability. The problem referred to as "known good die" for MCMs becomes "known good modules" for 3-D assemblies. Because a single 3-D assembly could contain dozens of layers and hundreds of

components, the problems of VLSI are only magnified.

3-D HETEROGENEOUS FRAMEWORKS

An initial examination of comprehensive application to 3-D packaging to an entire system was undertaken in the MiP project⁴. The study examined packaging of several representative system functions, including a cooled imaging sensor, inertial reference unit, analog and digital processing, power conversion, and rf telemetry. The program employed a many-layer 3-D edge-connected MCM assembly approach, as shown in Figure 9. In this approach, a number of layers (potentially dozens) are laminated together. The "monolithic" block is then

Figure 9. MiP 3-D microsystem.

laminated with a dielectric sheet that is processed with multilayer interconnections to form a layer-to-layer microbackplane. For each layer MiP employed a 1.6 inch basic element size, with 160 I/O per layer. In addition to routing I/O on two edges, I/O were redistributed over the module's surface (Figure 10a) to permit pre-test using an interposer mount to a temporary fixture (Figure 10b).

MiP Lessons Learned. The opportunities for synergism were clear. For example, cooled assemblies, such as focal plane arrays, could be exploited to vent waste heat through the remaining electronics assembly. Microbackplanes, given the lower average capacitance, could allow ICs to be redesigned to exploit higher performance and/or lower power. Thermal management structures could be used for provisional grounding planes.

To be sure, room for improvement existed. One of MiP's hallmarks, the "monolithic" integration of many individual MCMs and components, was also one of the most disconcerting features to potential users. The ability to separate the assembly into components was viewed as very important, since it allowed easy repair and upgrade.

Highly Integrated Packaging and Processing

Based on the precedents explored in the MiP program, a new effort, termed the Highly Integrated Packaging and Processing (HIPP) program, has been established to promote the development of a heterogeneous packaging framework for 3-D systems, as previously

Figure 10. MiP MCM pre-test system.

suggested. Two generic approaches for this framework, presented in Figure 11, illustrate the principle of an heterogeneous 3-D framework. In the "Type 1" approach, layers are stacked and interconnected incrementally using a plane-plane interconnection scheme. In the "Type 2" case, which uses edge-plane connections, a unibody package provides structural reinforcement for the overall assembly (other approaches use a sliding frame to expand or contract accordion-style as layers are added or removed). MCM

substrates of many forms may be inserted into the assembly.

Thermal management is facilitated by access plenums in one plane, while electrical interface is achieved on the other. This concept is shown for the Type 2 assembly in Figure 12. Thermal design could be reduced to a cookbook exercise in this vision of packaging: if a designer exceeds the standard heat-handling capacity based on empirical measurement and / or modeling, he chooses an improved thermal material or method and slides it into a "thermal drawer".

Electrical performance of HIPP approaches

Figure 11. 3-D heterogeneous packaging architectures: Type 1 (left) and Type 2 (right).

is potentially very high. Round-trip signal paths are shorter than average for normal PWB assemblies, allowing higher frequency performance to be achieved before transmission line effects dominate. The ability to reduce impedance uncertainties may actually improve the performance of instrumentation signals, and the reduced path-lengths of course contribute to reduced series loss. Another benefit of improved deterministic interconnect performance is in the controlled reduction of noise margin, allowing reduced voltage swings and hence lower power. Introduction of provision ground planes between layers of the HIPP assembly may make possible the formation of virtual Faraday cages around sensitive electronics. Some of these postulates have yet to be verified; current research programs

are expected to investigate swept frequency performance from dc to 10 GHz in a special form of Type 1 assembly. This work will lead to some basis of quantifying the interconnections of the HIPP "micro-backplane," leading to the specification of optimized drivers and receivers in ICs that drive from layer-to-layer. This exercise could lead to dramatic reductions in power.

Figure 12. (left) Thermal management and micro-backplane interface on a Type 2 assembly. (right) Substrate used for thermal evaluation.

The benefits of HIPP approaches to space are obvious: dramatic reductions in size, weight, and power. Less obvious are the efficiencies afforded for electronics that are susceptible to total ionizing radiation dose in space. The shielding mass required to totally encircle these electronics can be substantial, but with HIPP assemblies, the per-component shielding penalty is dramatically lower. Power reduction is possible to do systematic reductions in capacitance and voltage swing. HIPP approaches afford these opportunities without sacrificing the normal advantages associated with conventional electronics, such as modularity and multi-source availability due to a common denominator layer specifications.

"Acceleration" of HIPP density is provided for, as well. This can occur as new advances

in microelectronics and packaging occur, allowing increased capability within a HIPP framework. New advances in connectors and interposers can be strategically exploited, to create "backwards compatibility". While the intent of a HIPP approach is for a universal dense framework, it is nevertheless expected that a small family of HIPP sizes will be required; current discussions have revolved around 1", 1.6", and 2" square layer dimensions, with 300 - 1000 I/O per layer.

CONCLUSIONS

No clear trends in 3-D packaging exist except for simple memory stacks. Other approaches exist with the goal of increased density or performance, yet none have any significant acceptance. As such, little of the investments in these research activities are transferred, resulting in a diversity of very expensive prototypes.

Newer research efforts, such as MiP and HIPP, offer great flexibility with slight compromises in density. Such systems constitute a new approach to efficient system level packaging, possessing many of the features of larger standards such as VME, but at a fraction of the size and mass.

¹ Lyke, James C. "Packaging Technologies for Space-Based Microsystems and Their Elements", Chapter from *Microengineering Technology for Space Systems*, Aerospace Report No. ATR-95(8168)-2, 30 Sept 95

² Michael J. Little and C. Thomas Moberly. *Signal Processing Systems Packaging -1*, Rome Laboratory Technical Report RL-TR-92-95, April 1992

³ Mil-Std 1389D, Standard Electronic Module, Appendix E, also referred to as "SEM-E"

⁴ Scott Cannon, Jim Lyke, Jim Staggs, Daniel Watson, and Dane Fuller, "A Parallel C30 Architecture for Miniaturized 3-D Monolithic Packaging", presented at *Transputer Research and Applications Conference (NATUG-7)*, Oct 94.